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and cultural differences, constantly interact with learners' decision-making process in defining and orienting their language learning path . Although it is possible to eventually figure out the common or so-called universality of some language learning processes , it is probably an over-simplistic idea to assume that when two learners are at the same stage when learning a language will experience similar problems that similar solutions can address. In fact, research has proven that despite the possibility of classifying learning trajectories into stages, language learning trajectories are diverse .

Considering the complexity of learning trajectories, English language educators are expected to be more personalized and student-centered. Learner-centered language education should consider the needs of individual learners, and individual learning should be given special attention while cross-curricular knowledge is addressed and learning outcomes are maintained . It is expected that learner-centeredness and personification can allow learners to obtain richer experiences in a variety of settings, collaborate with experts in areas of personal interest, track and review their own learning across multiple sites and stages of learning, and access learning resources in formats and media appropriate to their language skills, abilities, and personal preferences . This new trend in language education entails discovering innovative methods to distribute learning materials and determining new ways to comprehend learners' abilities, resources, and interests outside the classroom .

Unfortunately, however humanistic this advocacy is, it is problematic when assessing individual needs and incorporating them into the classroom context, especially if the class consists of more than one student. Because each learner is fundamentally different, their outcomes may also be different. As teachers have to follow a predetermined syllabus, ready-made course book, and learning objectives, the absolute freedom they have to consider the authentic classroom context is often overlooked. With the current education system, the teachers are usually expected to be the captain who steers the ship using all the classroom pedagogical activities. Teachers must face the difficulty of sensitizing themselves and reacting to constantly changing learner needs. This article discusses the disadvantages of the current "teacher-should-know-all" model and proposes an alternative approach to restructuring language education that considers learners' affordance-based learning trajectories to allow language learners to self-regulate their linguistic development.

2. Teachers as Mr. and Ms. Know it All...oh really?

Given the complexities of learning paths, teachers are advised to arm themselves with an ever-expanding repertoire of teaching techniques and approaches in the hope of getting to know their students well enough to cater to different personalized moment-to-moment learning needs. When I raised the question of how teachers manage to get into learners' heads to know what they need and respond to these needs appropriately in a way that encourages individuals to move forward in a time-limited classroom at another international TESOL conference, the answer I received was "that is why you need to be a good

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teacher” (R. Ellis, 2022). It is expected that good teachers should go to great lengths to “know their students well” and be able to provide them with as various patterns of interaction and tasks as possible since there is no one-size-fits-all solution to all problems (Nguyen & Oliver, personal communication, November 17, 2022). On the other hand, how possible and practical those suggestions are, might be hard to confirm.

Despite those seemingly logical justifications for teachers’ efforts to become more benevolent and professionally competent, the moment-to-moment needs of each individual in a typical 30-student class and their constantly evolving here-and-now points of the learning path are virtually unknown to an ordinary teacher, despite how hard they try. Even in an imaginary classroom, when teachers have the mind-reading supernatural ability of a Vulcan mind-meld from the Star Trek film series, it is doubtful they can adapt their lesson plan to cope with floods of real-time variations of 30 people’s problems at once. Learning in a time-bound classroom may hardly be reflective and personalized since all the classroom members must act as selfless and disciplinary individuals and work towards the so-called common goals lest they be treated as the “black sheep” of the class. Thus, the “know your student well” statement seems no more than a humanistic call for the empowerment of teachers and students so that they may experiment with several possibilities for teacher practices that might be helpful to several groups of learners.

3. The Forged Democracy of the Conventional Education

In the institutional environment where formal schooling is time-bound, room for such freedom is much more limited. It is typical of schools and faculties to decide on their course books and syllabi that are compulsory for teachers and students to follow, not to mention the national curricula in many countries around the world . These so-called fundamentals of a conventional classroom give teachers and students little say in deciding content and delivery . It is not uncommon for teachers to be part of the syllabus design groups or the author of a course book. However, even when one or two teachers become part of the program development, what they contribute to their course books is restricted to their knowledge, experience, and the meaning-making ability of their realities. In other words, the teacher-designers chosen now hold the centralized power to impose their assumptions, which may or may not be scientifically backed up, on the whole school or even the whole nation regardless of the discrepancies among learning and teaching contexts.

For fear that teachers may deviate from the given syllabi and course books, there are appraisal mechanisms that force them to create lesson plans based on outcomes and objectives predetermined by the course designers . says: “If else fails, standardize. When no other solution appears possible, simply design everything the same way, so people only have to learn once.” Admittedly, the outcome-based lesson plans, which usually divide a language lesson into three parts, is to some extent helpful in

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guarantee that the teachers, not the learners, do not go too far from the expected teaching objectives and squander all the allocated time for a specific course. That is not to say that syllabi, course books, outcome-based and objective-based lesson planning do not contribute to education and pedagogy. These cultural artifacts have been playing a very important role in human civilization since the dawn of the educational system.

However, this article posits that every mechanism has its maximum capacity, including the current educational system. In its current form, language education might have reached its limits unless it is transformed into something else. Standards may make human life more manageable but hinder future development. The fact that educators and researchers are still trying to standardize course books and lesson plans while other fields have come to a stage when artificial intelligence has become more popular raised a question regarding whether education has undergone any substantial innovation, or at least renovation, since the last century. Many critics claim that the educational system is change-resistant. It is unfair to say education has not changed; however, the changes in education, including language education, are not significant enough to unleash its new potential compared to other fields in the digital age. It might be noteworthy that “Qualitative changes—in a manner exactly fixed for each case—can only occur by the quantitative addition or quantitative subtraction of matter or motion” (so-called energy). In particular, when educators make significant efforts to maintain the conventional approaches and artifacts, they might likely forget that what they need is more of a qualitative transformation than a quantitative addition that enables a new ‘plasma’ stage of education with a new overarching framework of educational theory and practice. There requires a more overarching term to explain a more holistic mechanism.

4. The Conceptualization of Affordances

The term *affordance* was coined by psychologist James J. Gibson in 1966. In an ecological context, Gibson defined affordances as the good and the bad an environment offers, provides, or furnishes its animals. However, this original definition of affordance remains ambiguous since if we define affordance as merely what the environment offers, there is a blurred distinction between affordances and potentials. Admittedly, if there is no clear differentiation between affordances and potentials, there is no need to reinvent the wheel.

However, it is not very sensible to separate affordance from its ecological perspective. Affordances are not solely the embedded characteristics of an object per se; they must, in fact, emerge from the ecological niche. For example, olive leaves have an inherent set of potentials (to be picked up by a human being to make a crown or to be picked for nest-building for birds, for example). However, there is hardly a bird that uses olive leaves to make its crown, or no human being would use olive leaves to build a nest. Thus, affordance is an iterative process of perceptions of potentials, actions, and consequences,

when an animal interact with objects of its environment within the sensorimotor and cognitive capacity of an animal .

More specifically, affordance is a process that starts with action potentials that emerge when an individual interacts with aspects of the world. Having apprehended an object or event in its current stage (firstness), an individual then comprehends what that object or event may mean to them, also known as semiosis, and what potentials that object or event may offer (secondness). These perceived and comprehended potentials may trigger both conscious and subconscious predictions of the possible actions with the same or different objects. These actions may be predicted with certain consequences when this individual opts for this (instead of that) action, which may indeed affect that individual again. The whole process, relative and adaptive to individuals, is affordance (see figure 1). If a second individual has an opportunity to take up, take in, collaborate, or discuss to apprehend and comprehend the affordances-through-interaction between the first individual and an object or event, another synchronization of affordances may also emerge, which also creates an opportunity for actions from the second individual per se (thirdness).

Figure 1. Affordances in interaction

It is, however, worth bearing in mind that what I explain in figure 1 is not aimed to provide an exhaustive and comprehensive explanation of all complicated cognitive and metacognitive processes that one’s brain goes through when interacting with the world. This figure is merely a relative demonstration of how affordance may emerge that is simplified enough to be comprehensible.

5. Linguistic Affordance

5.1 The problematic notion of comprehensible input and output

Imagine comprehensible input as an edible banana and the learner as a monkey in a

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language forest. If the banana is independent of the monkey's sensory system, it is hardly likely that the monkey will come and eat it. This is a logical flaw when one equates input with intake. Additionally, even if the monkey notices the existence of the apple, we cannot guarantee that any further actions from the monkey will crop up. This example justifies that input and noticing do not suffice unless there is a dynamic relationship between learners and learning opportunities. In other words, comprehensible input and notice are a necessity, not a sufficiency, for learners to take in the language. Also, the learner's linguistic system is by no means solely based on input, as their system is always more significant than the sum of its part. Otherwise, human beings cannot use their language to create literacy and artistic works. Swain and Lapkin (1995) proposed the output hypothesis to complement the idea that the input hypothesis offers, which puts forward the importance of production. Accordingly, as successful language users, learners must be able to construct the language. However, this theory again arbitrarily assumes the equivalence of acquisition and production. In reality, learners do not need to use a linguistic item to prove that they have learned it. Whether a learner produces a linguistic feature or not depends on their personal preference of how appropriate and necessary for them to use the language they learn. As to our example above, whether the monkey picks the banana, consumes it, saves it, or gives it to another banana depends on the squirrel's choice, not its ability. Undeniably, input, noticing, and output hypotheses significantly contribute to understanding language learning, just as we cannot deny the importance of apples in the monkey's food chain. However, the problems here lie in how the researchers use the terms rather than the knowledge they contribute.

5.2 The conceptualization of linguistic affordances

Given the issues of current terms used in second language learning, it is essential to consider another term that describes the process of how learners can actively pick up linguistic knowledge from the semiotic budget their environment offers. The notion of affordance has influenced many other sciences, including English language teaching (ELT) and second language acquisition. In language learning, affordances are the opportunities and challenges that learners perceive in the environment to learn a language (Van Lier, 2004). Within the ecological linguistic sense, affordances, offering potential learning opportunities or inhibitions, come from the learning environment's semiotic budget that allows language to emerge.

It is not a straightforward task to define linguistic affordance despite its popularity in recent years. I have to admit that the definition that people try to expand and stuff into the term "affordance" can be, like what takes about the constant competition to add excessively more and more features into a design, a function creep. The ongoing over-expansion of what one can define as "affordance" makes it a magical term that can refer to everything in the field or, blatantly, an over-swelling concept. For example, define affordances as "demands and requirements, opportunities and limitations, rejections

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and invitations, enablements and constraints” (p.34). Another example is Forrester (1999, as cited in) who says that affordance in language learning may include signal taking, back channeling, intonations, and other attitudinal markers. Although the world consists of interconnected systems, everything cannot be anything. Systems must be differentiable on their continuants, like the 2% difference in genome distinguishing chimpanzees and humans , or functions as functional wholes . Thus, overloading the term with linguistic affordance with too many sub-categories may dilute and mystify it.

Having previously defined affordance as a relative process in general, in this section, I would go a step further to place the definition of affordance in a linguistic context with caution so as not to create another bloating concept. However, admittedly, part of my definition of linguistic affordance is also based on Van Lier (2004), with some adaptations.

- a. Linguistic affordance is the relative relationship between perceptions of potentials, actions, and consequences when language users interact with a linguistic item in a semiotic niche.
- b. Linguistic affordance is perceivable when users can consciously or subconsciously participate in the meaning-making process (semiosis) and conclude with either various linguistic or non-linguistic actions.
- c. Linguistic affordance is hidden when language users cannot initiate the semiosis process without support from or observation of other members of the linguistic ecology.

Thus, support or observation of how others make sense of linguistic expressions and process outcomes may transform hidden linguistic affordances into perceivable ones. Hidden affordances usually occur when language users are, in 's term, unconsciously incompetent, in which situation the language users do not recognize their deficit and deny the usefulness of trying to process the linguistic items. However, unconscious incompetence works on an item basis rather than a learning trajectory or competence stage. Users may create possible actions and outcomes based on misunderstandings when engaging in hidden affordances. These affordances are usually too peripheral to notice but will later be adapted if the users gain enough exposure to actions other ecology members conventionally take.

Linguistic affordance is positive when language users can arrive at the meaning of a linguistic expression approximately similar to what other language users are conventionally and socially expected to comprehend and arrive at actions that comply with their values. They can also choose to sustain the meaning-making process if the expression has not been fully comprehended yet. The outcomes of these actions can promote further and more successful interactions or terminate that specific interaction. In either case, the language users can actively control possible actions based on the meaning-making process.

Linguistic affordance is negative when language learners try and fail in their meaning-making process; thus, their prediction of possible actions and related consequences might be an ineffective flee-

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fight-or-freeze response to escape from communication. Negative linguistic affordance might also occur when the expression is presented misleadingly or impedes possible actions from the addressees.

6. Affordance-based learning trajectories

6.1 Revisiting learning trajectories

Researchers view learning trajectories as conjectural or hypothetical model pathways or progressions of learning over periods that have been empirically validated. Similarly, in language education, according to Ellis (2015), language learning trajectories, language acquisition path, order of language acquisition, or sequence of language acquisition/learning is defined as how learners' interlanguage develops over time. It is believed that it is rigorous and customary for learning trajectories to be used to formulate and align curricula, teaching plans, and assessments. For nearly three decades, there have not been any significant changes in the definition of learning trajectory as defined by, stating that there can be a hypothetical pathway to determine a sequence of goals and activities during the thinking and learning process students might undergo. However, there is still doubt whether such a hypothetical pathway is universal for all learners, particularly language learners. Of course, learners may have similar learning stages if researchers will insist on classifying their linguistic development into stages. However, these classifications of human learning into stages would benefit structuralists who want to generalize the world more than the learners themselves. Universal learner trajectories with determined pre-fixed stages are more of a philosophical justification for similar characteristics of a sample rather than a practical solution.

On the contrary, the claim that all learners may have been through similar learning paths after researching some learner groups may pull researchers and educators into the trap of *argumentum ad ignorantiam*, which means that we conclude that something is right not because we can find comprehensive evidence to support it but because we believe in the presence of disconfirming evidence (Woods & Walton, 1978). Just as one wants to classify learning into stages and no one has figured out any different patterns does not mean that those different patterns do not exist. The idea that all humanity has universal learning trajectories is not much different from the claim that we all have an innate language device to process a universal language that Noam Chomsky suggested. However, this article is in no position to constitute any other voice in the debate about whether learning trajectories are universal since the academic world has been inundated with such discussion. As Ellis (2015, p. 125) puts it:

It is not easy to reconcile these different positions. They are based on different theoretical assumptions and have been researched using different methodological procedures. However, I find it difficult to accept that there are not major commonalities in the way in which all learners acquire a second language. Individual differences in acquisition sequences certainly do occur—in particular, due to the influence of the learner's first language—but the claim that

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there are universal paths in L2 acquisition constitutes a useful idealization.

The tricky part of Ellis (2015)'s position is that the universal path is a useful idealization. In fact, the question is whether what is called useful is vital in promoting language learning or is just a necessary administrative mechanism to keep the classroom model manageable. The belief that differences in language acquisition are particularly due to learners' first language is inadequate as learner variations are more of a combination of social, cultural, historical, psychological, and physical aspects. From learners' perspective, what they might need as motivation and encouragement to continue learning through tough times is appropriate moment-to-moment support for case-by-case issues than a general classification of their characteristics. Having said that, I have to agree that trying to find a reconciliation of opposite views might not contribute much to academia.

What matters more might be that language education may move from the current teacher-student paradigm to new paradigms that helps enhance learners' participation in the meaning-making and knowledge-seeking process rather than how language is acquired at different stages. With the aid of current technological innovations, such as artificial intelligence, virtual reality, machine learning, and the like, these new paradigms should likely allow pedagogical interventions to be adaptable to learning needs instead of administrative convenience. It is probable that education, particularly language education, could come to a stage when we can develop new learning paradigms based on the innovative deviation that learning and teaching are two non-linear processes. There may not be a causal relationship between them .

6.2 *Affordance-based language learning trajectories*

The aforementioned quest to seek new paradigms may be possible, and developing learning trajectories based on affordances may be an option. Affordance-based learning trajectory is nothing like a cut-and-dried learning path aiming at finding the same path for every learner. Instead, it is a complex, dynamic, open system that learners need to both simultaneously and consequently deal with the affordances around them. This is an infinite quest that gives learners absolute freedom to deal with linguistic knowledge within their sensorimotor and cognitive capacity within their linguistic niche.

As learners interact with the semiotic budget of the new language, they will notice different affordances, namely perceivable, hidden, positive, and negative. It is the learners who recognize the ratios between types of affordances that they encounter during their learning process. Perceivable and positive affordances might benefit learners as they can comprehend linguistic items and decide on appropriate actions that continue the interaction. If the relationship between a learner and a linguistic expression is both perceivable and positive, the learners can use that expression appropriately on demand.

In contrast, learners cannot start to apprehend the hidden affordances unless they observe or receive support from others ecology members to process their linguistic items. This case means that a

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linguistic expression can be hidden for one but perceivable for others. Observing others' affordances can help knowledge emerge inside the learners, emphasizing the importance of real human networks. This process of transforming hidden affordances into something perceivable is perhaps what calls incidental learning or concrete experience in the words of . Hidden affordances may also transform into perceivable affordances of the more knowledgeable other through instructional scaffolding from the perspective of Vygotsky . When learners can perceive an affordance but cannot produce appropriate linguistic actions and cannot predict the outcomes related to their action, the affordance is negative. Linguistic affordances can begin as hidden and then become perceivable but end up as negative ones. In this case, it means either that the learners have not been socio-culturally experienced enough to deal with the expression, or what learners can perceive of the linguistic expression is not at its optimal stages that the brain can fully comprehend and analyze to yield appropriate responses. If the former is true, then learners may also seek helps and supports from other members of the ecology. In reverse, when perceptions of the linguistic item are not optimal, a fine-tuning effort, or input enhancement as cognitive linguists may call it, can be made to the linguistic items themselves or learners' cognition. Some example of fine-tuning can be found in language research about Verbotonalism when low-pass filtering (<320Hz) highlights that the melody of the language can be optimal for learning and teaching intonation . Such fine-tuning is capable, with human efforts. However, it would be more manageable if learning trajectories were tracked by a self-regulated learning platform capable of providing fine-tuned linguistic items as a system I would briefly introduce in the next session.

Overall, learner trajectory is not expected to produce a one-size-fits-all learning path that fosters curriculum design, course book selection, or lesson planning. Instead, by introducing the affordance-based learning trajectory, this article advocates a paradigm where learning is self-regulated, and learners' trajectories are their constant interactions with different types of affordances so that hidden can become perceivable and negative can become positive affordances.

7. A glimpse into a system of the future: A rhizomatic perspective

This article has mentioned a future system that can support learners' linguistic development or their trajectories. Actually, the idea of such a system that can fine-tune linguistic affordances is not very novel. introduce a "fragment of a rhizomatic learning environment for foreign culture/language learning." The learner is in charge of the network directly, via a set of tools, or through the possible connections of each node. From an ecological perspective, I modify what Lian and Moore pioneer and can introduce an affordance-based system that includes three main function sub-systems (see figure 2).

Figure 2. An affordance-based learning environment

Within this environment, learners are provided personalized affordance-based fine-tuning devices or platforms that can provide them with a linguistic expression on demand. If regulated by artificial intelligence, besides receiving requests from the learners when learners are working with their linguistic affordances, this sub-system can analyze learning affordances and enhances itself to meet adapt learners' constantly changing learning trajectories. As learners interact with the system, learning affordances also emerge. These may not be linguistic affordances but are learning affordances that promote more learning opportunities (positive affordances) or allow the platforms to recognize the challenges the learners face from using the platforms (negative affordances). When these linguistic and learning affordances are tracked, the machine learning process can enhance the system to provide the most relevant resources for learners' linguistic development. At this time, the dual purpose of personalizing education and keeping the learning model manageable can be fulfilled.

The baseline is, in this environment, each node is much more intricate than the graphic suggests. This system may have been just a figment of imagination for some readers ten or twenty years ago, but with the current technological advancement at the time I am writing this article, it is possible. When the system is smart enough, it can hopefully suggest what tools the students might need. The role of teachers in the new paradigm is not solely about teaching. Instead, they will be part of the decision support system that students can consult when it comes to issues related to the ecology that are

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incompressible by machines, for example, emotions of language use. They can also be the mastermind behind how the education system should evolve on a microscale rather than solely focus on minor point-by-point planning in the traditional classroom. Teachers eventually take up the consultant role for students and the affordance-based AI system. Their work will highly likely shift from what is currently functional to someone more metacognitive in the new paradigm. Last but by no means least, the real human networks are where the learners fully and socially function. Hardly can learners notice their limitations until they are functioning. As they notice the gaps in their knowledge and how others use the language, hidden affordances become perceivable. Learners can learn language from human networks, bring problems that they encounter in the human network to personalized affordance-based fine-tuning devices, or even seeks advice from the decision support system. When affordance-based fine-tuning devices are connected to the internet systems where virtual networks of humanity, the devices can also become a learner and learn from our social, cultural, and historical wisdom that, in turn, will benefit the learners.

8. Conclusion

In this article, I have first discussed two opposing schools of thought about learning trajectories and arrived at the position that moment-to-moment needs that shape individual learning trajectories might be beyond teachers' control. As the universal language learning path is still a controversial discourse, the self-assuring advice that good teachers should be adaptive and know their students well does not contribute much to the intellectual values of the language education field. Then this article has provided us with a critical reflection on the forged democracy of the educational system that humanity currently experiences. As an alternative, affordance-based language education is expected to fight off that inertia of language education and allow learners to steer their own learning path. Linguistic affordances, which can be hidden, perceivable, negative, and positive, emerge when human beings interact with the semiotic budget, and therefore, become part of the learners' dynamic and personalized learning trajectories. The article also proposed a learning environment comprised of personalized affordance-based fine-tuning devices, a decision support system, and real human networks, which would allow learners to gain more control over their learning compared to the conventional education paradigm.

9. References

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Brief Bio

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